

Strategies for Managing Open Innovation in SMEs in Bangladesh and the Contribution of SMEs to the National Economy: An Observational Study

Most. Tahura Pervin, Razia Begum, & Bipul Kumar Sarker

Abstract

Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs) are the far-reaching evolution in the arena of open innovation which is an emerging concept that attracts a lot of entrepreneurs in Bangladesh. Open innovation has been immensely implemented in small and medium enterprises with the intention of impressing business uplift, financial and economic empowerment. SMEs and Open Innovation gathers data & information in which SMEs can put open innovation strategies to development by entrepreneurial, institutional, and exploratory study. The motto of this study is to make policy, economic, and cultural issues, including various privileges and challenges adjoining open innovation strategies in Bangladesh SMEs sector. A quantitative method was chosen to make this study a success. Specifically, a structured interview method has been followed to collect data from primary sources to provide a clear picture of the development of this industry through the application of innovative approaches to the management strategy of SMEs in Bangladesh. Data was collected from eighty respondents from three different cities (Dhaka, Gazipur, and Narsingdi) using the convenience sampling technique (non-probability sampling). Convenient sampling techniques were applied to draw samples to ensure representation of all types of companies. Data was analyzed regarding of frequency, percentage, regression analysis, and ANOVA using SPSS.

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Introduction:

According to the World Bank announcement, Bangladesh has already grown into a middle income country. Small and medium enterprises have a huge contribution to this outstanding achievement. One of the driving forces of this economic development is the small and medium enterprises (SMEs). The SME sector can play an important role in achieving economic growth, eliminating poverty, eliminating unemployment, reducing regional inequality, equality for women and empowering women. The smooth development of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) can accelerate economic development. Innovative capabilities are immense among the entrepreneurs of the country. Hard work and strong self-esteem can influence the sector and further accelerate the socio-economic condition of the country. Because about 80% of the country's industrial enterprises are small and medium enterprises.

Innovation:

There is a long discussion about how innovation works in the SME sector of Bangladesh. Although innovation is not a new concept, innovation has begun long ago in small and medium industries in Bangladesh. There are various types of literature on innovation that provide ideas about different definitions and methods of innovation. In its broadest sense, the word comes from Latin "Innovare", meaning 'to create new things or to develop new ideas' (Tid and Besent, 2009, page 16). When we talk about innovation, we cannot ignore the "father's" view of innovation research - Joseph Schumpeter. According to him, the innovation is to develop new or significant advanced products or services, to introduce new manufacturing methods, to open new markets, to identify new sources of raw material supply or to create new industrial structures (Sledzik, 2013, p. 90).

Open Innovation:

Open Innovation implies opening up the innovation procedure beyond organization periphery so as to build one's own innovation potential through dynamic key utilization of the circumstance.

Place of innovation = inside and outside the company

Open innovation is defined as "the purposive inflows and outflows of information to accelerate inner innovation, and expand the markets for external use of innovation, respectively" (Chesbrough et al., 2006). Based on this definition which highlights the mobility of knowledge, a typology appeared which divides OI in in-bound and out-bound relying on the path of knowledge glide (Chesbrough and Brunswicker, 2013). In-bound OI refers to things to do that focus on the acquisition of external understanding "in-sourcing", "R&D collaboration", "mergers and acquisitions" and "customer involvement" falls into this category. Out-bound OI refers to expertise exploitation to trading in a number ways: "Licensing-out", "spin-off" and "open-sourcing". Schilling (2013) defines innovation as "the practical implementation of a thought into a new device or process" and argues that "innovation starts with the generation of new ideas". One of the typologies most used in literature is the dichotomy of radical versus incremental innovation; the place radical improvements refer to necessary changes in science with clear departures from current practices, whereas incremental improvements are minor changes or upgrades in the contemporary science (Dewar & Dutton, 1986; Ettl, 1983).

Open Innovation in SME:

Van de Vrande et al. (2009) show that larger firms adopt open innovation to a larger extent than SMEs. The authors identified several managerial and organizational challenges perceived by SMEs in adopting open innovation practices that involve their customers: (1) Organizational and cultural barriers that include the balance between daily

tasks and the innovation project, communication problems, the alignment with partners, and the organization of the open innovation activity itself; (2) Resources in terms of the costs and the time required by the activity; (3) Intellectual property rights that raise the question of the ownership of ideas, and developed, and commercialized innovations especially in cases where different parties are cooperating; (4) Adoption problems, e.g., the misinterpretation of customer requirements; and (5) Demand of customers that might be too specific or the innovation seems to not fit the desired market. Compared to large enterprises, SMEs possess less external relations with innovation partners beyond their own business sector. Consequently, the potential to exchange innovation-related information and to collaborate in innovation projects is restricted (Kaufmann & Tödting, 2002). According to Kaufmann and Tödting (2002, p. 151) there are a limited number of employees “who are able to act as nodes establishing and maintaining links to innovation networks”. A solution to overcome the limited resources of SME’s regarding innovation is to use the input and services of external partners or collaborations that operate as intermediaries to facilitate innovation (Lee et al., 2010).

Definition of SME:

SME definitions depend on the criteria applied in different countries such as number of employees, value of assets, sales and output amount, etc (Cunningham & Rowley, 2008). These definitions vary from one country to another, even within the country. Following are the definitions of SMEs given by different institutions in Bangladesh:

As per Bangladesh Bank:

Small Enterprises:

Small Enterprise refers to the firm/business which is not a public limited company. A firm or business might be characterized as small enterprises if the following criteria are satisfied:

Table 01: Definition of SME as per the Bangladesh Bank (Small Enterprises)

Serial No.	Sector	Fixed Asset other than Land and Building (Tk.)	Employed Manpower (not above)
1	Service	50,000 – 50,00,000	25
2	Business	50,000 – 50,00,000	25
3	Industrial	50,000 – 15,000,000	50

Table 02: Definition of SME as per the Bangladesh Bank (Medium Enterprise):

Nature of Enterprise	Value of Asset (excluding land & building)	Manpower	Turnover
Manufacturing	BDT 100000 to 5,0000000	Maximum 300	BDT 500000 to 200000000
Trading	BDT 100000 to 30000000	Maximum 50	
Service	BDT 100000 to 10000000	Maximum 75	

Source: Bangladesh Bank (Small and Medium Enterprises Credit Policies and Programmes, 2010)

National Industrial policy (2016):

The need to set a single definition of SMEs for the integration and evaluation of SMEs' activities and the contribution of SMEs to the economy is intensely felt. For this purpose, a single definition of SME has been provided in National Policy 2016. This definition is now

being followed by all organizations involved with SMEs. If a single definition is used, the contribution of the SME sector to the economy can be assessed as well.

Table 03: Definition of SME as per the Industrial Policy 2016 of the Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh is given below:

S.L	Type of Industry		The amount of investment (Replacement cost and value of fixed assets, excluding land and factory buildings)	Number of employed workers
1	Cottage Industry		Below 10 lakh	number of workers not exceed 15
2	Micro Industry		10 lakh to 75 lakh	16 to 30
3	Small Industry	Manufacturing	75 lakh to 15 crore	31 to 120
4	Medium Industry	Service	10 lakh to 2 crore	16 to 50
		Manufacturing	15 crore to 50 crore	121 to 300
5	Large Industry	Service	2 crore to 30 crore	51 to 120
		Manufacturing	More than 50 crore	More than 300
		Service	More than 30 crore	More than 120

Source: National Industrial policy (2016)

History and growing development of small and medium industries in Bangladesh

The small and medium industries of Bangladesh have a glorious history. Once upon a time the famous muslin cloth was made in this country. Traditional Jamdani, Nakshikantha, Shitalpati, Bamboo and cane materials are still carrying the tradition of small and medium industry, even if the muslin extinction is extinct. There is no panic if there is a silent revolution between the small and medium industries in the country now. This has been possible through the development of various types of farms, handicrafts, package industries, starting from poultry industry. At present, this industry has spread across the country. Economy scenario has changed to innovate, manufacture and market small parts of domestic technology.

Present Scenario of SME

In the last decade, Bangladesh's economy has achieved an annual growth rate of around 7 percent. Bangladesh achieved the status of middle-income country in 2018. In the last year of the seventh Five-Year Plan, the target of achieving 8.13 percent GDP growth in the year 2019 has been set. Bangladesh wants to be promoted to middle-income countries by 2021 and therefore requires an environmentally friendly environment capable of achieving inclusive, sustainable and adaptable growth. Industrialization is the key tool for achieving higher economic growth and creating jobs. According to many, Bangladesh's growing economic growth is at the root of growing non-agricultural activities. In the last decade, the manufacturing sector has grown at 7.74 percent and the service sector has been 7 percent. Currently, 35.14 percent of the contribution of industry sector to GDP, which was 21.4 percent in 1990, On the other hand, the contribution of service sector to the country's total GDP is 55.38 percent. The contribution of agriculture to the GDP in the last two years has been drastically reduced. Falling from 29.23 percent in 1990 to 13.31 percent in 2018-19 Even though agricultural contributions are reduced in GDP, agriculture is still the biggest source of employment (about 48 percent). Although a major source of agricultural employment, the main driving force of growth is the industrial sector. The contribution of the industrial sector to the country's total GDP is 35.14 percent. But the industry sector has not yet been able to utilize its potential in organizing surplus labor force for the country's huge agricultural sector. In the developing countries like Bangladesh, SME sector is expected to

have the potential to become the main tool of supporting the development and growth of the manufacturing sector as well as in addition to the work of surplus labor force in agricultural sector.

Table 4: Average growth rate of major sectors of GDP and economy (%)

Year	Total GDP growth	Sector wise GDP growth		
		Agricultural	Industry	Services
2010/11	6.64	4.46	9.02	6.22
2013/14	6.15	5.37	8.16	5.62
2014/15	6.54	3.33	9.67	5.80
2015/16	7.11	2.79	11.09	6.25
2016/17	7.28	2.97	10.22	6.69
2017/18	7.86	4.19	12.06	6.39
2018/19	8.13	3.51	13.02	7.00

Source: Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (BBS)

Table 5: Dedicated contribution to GDP (%)

Sector	Share (in percent)								
	1990/91	2000/01	2010/11	2013/14	2014/15	2015/16	2016/17	2017/18	2018/19
Agriculture	29.23	25.03	18.01	16.50	16.00	15.35	14.74	14.23	13.31
Industry	21.04	26.20	27.38	29.55	30.42	31.54	32.42	33.66	35.14
Service	49.73	48.77	54.61	53.15	53.58	53.12	52.85	52.11	55.38

Source: Bangladesh Economic Review 2019

Literature Review:

The thought “strategic management” deals with how corporations boost sustainable aggressive benefits resulting in the introduction of price (Ramachandran, Mukherji & Sud, 2006). Ireland, Hitt et al. (2001) opined that strategic administration can be viewed as putting the context for owners-manager behavior, i.e. the exploitation of opportunities. These include sources for consideration and implementation of key dreams and initiatives adopted by a company's final administration on behalf of its owners based on the evaluation of the competitive internal and external environment. More importantly, strategic administration affords normal course to the organization and involves specifying the organization's objectives, creating long-term policies and plans designed to reap these objectives, and then allocating assets to enforce the plans. Educators and organizations have created a number of frameworks to support strategic selection in the context of complex environments and competitive dynamics (Ghemawat, 2002). The concept “strategic management” is not static in nature; the fashions frequently encompass a comments loop to display execution and inform the subsequent round of planning (Lamb, 1984; and Hill & Gareth, 2012). More so, it assists companies to make fine selections and techniques with the aid of staying alert to the threats and possibilities in an unsure and dynamic environment. Furthermore, strategic management includes the associated standards of strategic planning and strategic thinking. Strategic planning refers to the nature of the analytical and formal processes for producing data, and the analysis used as input for strategic thinking, which involves the synthesis of data as a result of the strategy. Strategic planning may additionally refer to manipulate mechanisms used to put in force the method as soon as it is determined. In other words, strategic planning takes place around the strategic questioning or strategy making recreation. They similarly noted that strategic management is regularly described as involving two predominant processes: formula and implementation of strategy. Consequently, the method

of method involves analyzing the surroundings in which the employer operates, then making a collection of strategic choices about how the company will compete. However, formulation ends with a sequence of desires or goals and measures for the organization to pursue. Moreover, the 2nd principal system of strategic administration "implementation" involves decisions related to how the organization's assets (i.e., people, technique and IT systems) will be aligned and mobilized in the direction of the objectives. As a result, the implementation outcomes in how the organization's assets are structured (such as by means of product or provider or geography), management arrangements, communication, incentives, and monitoring mechanisms to song development towards objectives, etc. Past research have argued that strategic management research is radically concerned with figuring out variations amongst enterprises" performance by means of analyzing their efforts to advance sustainable competitive advantages as determinants of their capability to create value (Ireland, Hitt & Simon, 2003) and identifying the report retaining thing that make a contribution to a profitable monetary administration (Osotimehin et al., 2012).

Methodology:

The study collected data from SME entrepreneurs from three different regions of Bangladesh. Information has been collected from SMEs listed organization in all these regions. The data collection has been done with the use of structured questionnaires. The questions of the questionnaires include open-ended questions, close-ended questions, multiple-choice questions and questions based on five point Likert scale. This method can generate less missed information compared with online survey, telephone surveys, and mail surveys. Moreover, the researcher or the research assistant ensures whether the respondents properly completed the questionnaire or not which reduces time consumption in rechecking of the data. According to economic census 2013, total number of establishments/firms are 78,18,565 among them 8,66,424 firms are SMEs (859,318 small and 7106 medium) and they are owned by sole ownership, partnership, private, company, government foreign, co-operative, non-profit organization and expatriate type forms. Of them, 93.6 percent are small and 6.4 percent are medium. Hence, target population is 866,424, some selection a criterion has been taken for getting more relevant information. The method of convenience sampling was employed in arriving at the 80 SMEs, which the researchers believe possesses the experience relevant for this study and who have sufficient time and was willing to participate (Morse, 1998). The reason for using the convenient sample technique in data collection in this study is because of the not available complete frame about Bangladesh SME. The primary focus of this study is to investigate whether the SMEs in Bangladesh are adopting the open innovation, and then identify the management strategies for adopting the open innovation in Bangladesh.

Result and Discussion

Demographic Characteristics

The result (table 6) shows that this type of business is dominated by male in rural communities. In the same vein, majority of the merchants were from the group 31-40. The effects additionally divulge that the traders had formal schooling and majority of the merchants have masters degree. It can also see that the majority of the traders dealt in a variety of items and operated by and large from their shops. Bank and family help have been the essential supply of their capital. In the identical vein, majority of the SMEs have been in commercial enterprise for 5 to 15 years business experience. Also, the traders offered to their

clients both money and on credit score and purchased a higher proportion of their goods with cash.

Table 6: Measures of the Constructs and Descriptive Statistics

		Frequency	Percentage
Age of Owner	Up to 30	24	30.00
	31 to 40	30	37.50
	41 to 50	18	22.50
	Above 50	8	10.00
Gender of the ownership	Male	67	83.75
	Female	13	16.25
Level of education	Up to SSC	9	11.25
	Up to HSC	16	20.00
	Up to Graduation (Hons./Degree)	25	31.25
	Masters	30	37.50
Types of Business	Manufacturing	35	43.75
	Services	18	22.50
	Software Development	1	1.250
	Knowledge intensive services (Education, Health Care, and Consultancy)	4	5.00
	Pharmaceutical & Chemical	7	8.75
	Textile	6	7.50
	Leather & Leather goods	3	3.75
	Other	6	7.50
Age of Organization	Less than five years	22	27.50
	Between 5-15 years	36	45.00
	Between 15-30 years	21	26.25
	More than 30 years	1	1.25
Location of organization	Dhaka	72	90.00
	Gazipur	5	6.25
	Narshingdi	3	3.75
The sources of fund of the organization	Own	29	36.25
	Loan	48	60.00
	Other	3	3.75

Factor Loading:

Table 7: Factor Loading

Open Innovation (OI)	Factor Loadings	Strategies Factors	Factor Loadings
Collecting new developmental ideas	0.71	Technology	0.85
To have a better understanding of customer needs & expectations	0.69	Competition	0.82
Access to new technologies or technical knowledge used in the firm	0.59	Cost leadership	0.77
Improving the efficiency of the organization	0.59	Market leadership	0.77
Removal of complex investment risk	0.54	Entry into international market	0.72
Strengthen relationships with suppliers/customers/distributors	0.50	Product/service development	0.68
Recovery of intellectual property & patents.	0.70	Networking	0.50
Acquiring new sources of knowledge & technology from external partners to incorporate those developed internally.	0.60	Management expertise & confidence to build up training to adapt OI	0.79
Sharing internal technology & knowledge to others.	0.50	Government incentive planning	0.71

Combining internal and external knowledge & technology to make a new path of development	0.59	To have a better understanding of customer needs & expectations	0.69
		Access to new technologies or technical knowledge used in the firm	0.50
		Strengthen relationships with suppliers	0.74

Management Strategies Factors for Adopting Open Innovation

This scale was used to measure management strategies factors and the responses were rated on the Likert-scale format, with answers ranging from 1-5 (1= strongly disagree and 5= strongly agree). The psychometric properties of the instrument were evaluated in terms of reliability. Cronbach's alpha values were calculated for all multi-item variables. The entire instrument as well as the individual variables exceeded the minimum alpha of 0.694 which is equivalent to 0.7 and According to Van Der Wal, achieved the acceptable reliability levels ranged from 0.7 to 0.80 (Van Der Wal, 2001).

Hypothesis 01: Management Strategies factors for Adopting Open Innovation in SMEs of Bangladesh

Hypothesis one states that "There is no significant relationship between management strategies factors for adopting open innovation in SMEs of Bangladesh". This hypothesis objective was to determine if strategies is significantly related to adopted open innovation in SMEs in Bangladesh. The result in table 8(c) exposed to view that motivating factors and strategies is significantly (F-ratio = 8.915; 0.00) related to adopted open innovation in SMEs in Bangladesh.

i. Model Specification

Mathematically, the model is expressed as follows:

$$OI = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \beta_5X_5 + \beta_6X_6 + \beta_7X_7 + \beta_8X_8 + \beta_9X_9 + \beta_{10}X_{10} + \beta_{11}X_{11} + \beta_{12}X_{12} + \epsilon$$

Where;

OI= Open Innovation;

X_1 = Strengthen relationships with suppliers;

X_2 = Cost leadership;

X_3 = Competition;

X_4 = Access to new technologies or technical knowledge used in the firm;

X_5 = Entry into international market;

X_6 = Government incentive planning;

X_7 = To have a better understanding of customer needs & expectations;

X_8 = Technology;

X_9 = Management expertise & confidence to build up training to adapt OI;

X_{10} = Networking;

X_{11} = Market leadership;

X_{12} = Product/service development;

β_0 = Regression constant (intercept);

β_1 --- β_{12} = Regression coefficients,

ϵ = Error term

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics was conducted to observe the distribution between strategies and open innovation data. Table 8(a) shows the summary of the descriptive statistics.

Table 8(a): Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Strategies Factors	80	4.00	5.00	4.55	0.24
Open Innovation	80	3.33	5.00	4.63	0.29
Valid N (listwise)	80				

Source: Survey Data, 2019

The study sample consisted of 80 participants. The independent variable, management strategies factors ranged from 4.00 to 5.00 with a mean of 4.55 and a standard deviation of 0.24. The dependent variable, open innovation ranged from 3.33 to 5.00 with a mean of 4.63 and a standard deviation of 0.29.

Table 8.(b): Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.784 ^a	0.615	0.546	0.19636

a. **Predictors(Constant):** Strengthen relationships with suppliers, Cost leadership, Competition, Access to new technologies or technical knowledge used in the firm, Entry into international market, Government incentive planning, To have a better understanding of customer needs & expectations, Technology, Management expertise & confidence to build up training to adapt OI, Networking, Market leadership, Product/service development

b. **Dependent Variable:** Open Innovation

Source: Survey Data, 2019

The coefficient of determination is 0.615 which means that the independent variable can explain 61.5% of the variation of the dependent variable. Therefore, about 61.5% of the total variation in the open innovation data is explained by management strategies factors. The regression equation appears to be very useful for making predictions since the value of R^2 is greater than 0.5.

Hypothesis Testing: ANOVA

Table 8.(c): Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4.125	12	0.344	8.915	0.000 ^a
	Residual	2.583	67	0.039		
	Total	6.708	79			

a. **Dependent Variable:** Open Innovation. Statistical Significance at 5%

b. **Predictors (Constant):** Strengthen relationships with suppliers, Cost leadership, Competition, Access to new technologies or technical knowledge used in the firm, Entry into international market, Government incentive planning, To have a better understanding of customer needs & expectations, Technology, Management expertise & confidence to build up training to adapt OI, Networking, Market leadership, Product/service development

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2019. Statistical Significance at 5%

Table 8(d): Multiple Regression showing the Motivating Factors and Strategies for Adopting Open Innovation in SMEs of Bangladesh

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	-0.294	0.559		-0.525	0.601
Technology	0.315	0.080	0.515	3.964	0.000
Competition	0.259	0.065	0.427	3.961	0.000
Cost leadership	0.009	0.040	0.019	0.221	0.826
Market leadership	0.128	0.078	0.221	1.652	0.103
Entry into international market	0.276	0.065	0.476	4.247	0.000
Product/service development	-0.045	0.084	-0.078	-0.540	0.591
Networking	0.014	0.075	0.024	0.187	0.852
Management expertise & confidence to build up training to adapt OI	-0.050	0.068	-0.085	-0.745	0.459
Government incentive planning	0.024	0.056	0.041	0.434	0.666
To have a better understanding of customer needs & expectations	0.059	0.064	0.097	0.930	0.355
Access to new technologies or technical knowledge used in the firm	0.092	0.055	0.155	1.678	0.098
Strengthen relationships with suppliers	-0.010	0.054	-0.017	-0.188	0.851

a. **Dependent Variable:** Open Innovation. Statistical Significance at 5%
Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2019.

In order to examine the effect of management strategies factors in SMEs in Bangladesh to adopted open innovation, multiple regression analysis technique was applied to test the data collected and the result presented on the table 8(a), table 8(b), table 8(c), and table 8(d) shows above. From table 8(b) it was observed that the identified management strategies factors as a construct accounted for a total of 61.5% ($R^2 = 0.615$) of the adopt open innovation within the period of the study. The model was confirmed with an F value of $(12, 67) = 8.915$ which was significant at 5% level of significance meaning that the model had the ability of capturing the contribution. This implies that management strategies factors jointly influence to adopt open innovation in SMEs in Bangladesh at 5% level of significant.

In determining the effect of the technology while holding the others constant, the study observed that technology accounted for a variation of 0.315 of the adopting open innovation and this was the highest among other at 5% level of significance with t-value of 3.964. The result suggested that the technology effect was not new to the respondents. Observations show that small and medium enterprises already had an idea of how to use technology in open innovation. This study advises SME entrepreneurs to increase their efficiency in the proper application of technology to open innovation before starting a business. The effect of competition on adopting open innovation, while holding other factors constant, was the study observed to be positive that competition accounted for a variation of 0.259 of the adopting open innovation and this was the 3rd highest among other at 5% level of significance with t-value is 3.961. The effect of entry into the international market on adopting open innovation, while holding other factors constant, was the study observed to be positive that entry into the international market accounted for a variation of 0.276 of the adopting open innovation and this was the 2nd highest among other at 5% level of significance with t-value is 4.247. All of the remaining items are statistically insignificant.

Conclusion:

Most SMEs operating in Bangladesh have no desire to fail due to the limited funding for open innovation. Although SME industry entrepreneurs in Bangladesh have commercially viable technology, most SME companies suffer from lack of complementary assets such as skills, market leadership, networking, access to new technologies, strengthening relationships with suppliers, manufacturing plants, marketing capabilities, and distribution channels for commercialization. The context is a bit different in recent times. Now, there are many organizations that are spending money for open innovation and taking risks for innovation. The need to reduce production costs and increase the importance of cooperation during the early stages of commercialization or commercialization of new products through open innovation has increased the importance of SME industries in Bangladesh. Therefore, innovative SMEs need to adopt open innovation approach to enter the technology and overseas market in SME industries through network and mutual cooperation with other SMEs and companies.

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